

LipAgg social media accounts and website live

Deliverable number: D5.1

HORIZON EUROPE-MSCA-2024-Doctoral Network

LipAgg
DOCTORAL NETWORK
ON AMYLOID PROTEIN

**Funded by
the European Union**

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LipAgg social media accounts and website

The LipAgg social media accounts and website are designed to **promote the project and disseminate its results** throughout its duration in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. They provide targeted information to **a wide range of audiences, including the scientific community, the partners, the media and the general public.**

LipAgg ensures that its research outputs follow **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and that its communication activities reach a wide audience.

To this end, LipAgg has developed:

- a dedicated website
- a LinkedIn profile
- a Zenodo repository

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1. Introduction

LipAgg is a Doctoral Network project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement ID: 101227450.

The LipAgg project is a 4-year project starting in March 2026 and ending in February 2030. This is a collaborative project supporting 15 Doctoral Candidates funded by Horizon Europe.

The project seeks to unravel the structural complexities of amyloid protein-lipid aggregates and investigate their role in pathological aggregation, cellular toxicity, and intercellular spread. Focusing on key human amyloid proteins—amylin (IAPP), amyloid beta (A β), and α -synuclein (α S)—linked to type 2 diabetes (T2D), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and Parkinson's disease (PD), respectively, the project builds on recent discoveries made by the consortium.

LipAgg consortium involves a total of 23 participants (8 beneficiaries – 15 partners) from 6 European countries: France, Germany, Italy, Sweden, Denmark and the Netherlands.

This deliverable presents the website, social media and open science profiles established for the LipAgg project. These digital tools will become available from Month 2 of the project and will play a key role in promoting the project, supporting recruitment activities, and dissemination of the scientific result.

From now on, the social media profiles are already promoting the LipAgg project, spreading the launch since the publication about the kick-off meeting, and increasing exposure for the recruitment of 15 doctoral positions.

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2. Visual identity: logo and graphic charter

The initial LipAgg logo was created before the official start of the project as a key communication element.

- **LipAgg logo:** The left side represents lipids, while the right side illustrates the aggregation phenomena, reflecting the core scientific focus of the project.
- **visual of the eight Principal Investigators:** this image aims to highlight the researchers involved in the project, thereby contributing to its visibility and human dimension. The circular design symbolizes unity, collaboration, and the continuous exchange of knowledge within the network.

The initial logos developed by the Principal Investigators and Hartmut Sebesse (MPINA, Germany), were subsequently modified with a neutral palette of blue tones, complemented by yellow highlights.

The LipAgg visual identity was defined to establish a coherent, consistent, and recognizable image. It supports clear communication across all materials while reinforcing the project's scientific positioning.

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3. LipAgg website

The LipAgg website (<https://LipAgg.eu/>) has been developed to provide information and resources to a variety of audiences, including the general public, students, the scientific community, and project partners.

It serves as a central component of the project's communication strategy and is based on the following principles:

- **clear and concise communication**, with a straightforward structure of information, well-organized sections, and intuitive navigation across different tabs.
- **neutral and consistent visual identity**, based on shades of blue, ensuring a professional and coherent presentation.
- **user-friendly and functional design**, with a structured presentation of themes and direct access to application processes.
- **sobriety and readability of content**, supported by a clean layout and restrained use of colors to enhance information visibility.
- **improved readability through typography**, using sans-serif fonts to ensure clarity and ease of reading across all devices.

The website, developed using WordPress, acts as a comprehensive repository of project-related information and adds a Brevo plugin for newsletter dissemination.

The website provides an overview of:

- the LipAgg **project summary**
- the **consortium's** composition (Team as beneficiaries and partners)
- all **Doctoral network positions**, with a list of the 15 PhD offers (including detailed description for each DC, the host institutions, partners and supervisor) with a direct link to apply
- a **communication** section (for news, events and dissemination)

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Website Structure:

HOME	Project summary and interactive European map of the consortium
PROJECTS /Apply now	All the doctoral Network projects, eligibility, requirements and a detail of each project with a “apply now” link
TEAM	Profiles and biographies of key members (Coordinator, Project Manager, Principal Investigators)
PARTNERS	List of associated partners with links to their websites
FELLOWS	Section to be completed (expected September)
NEWS & EVENTS	List of news and events

The design of the LipAgg project website is fully embedded in the definition of the LipAgg visual identity.

The service provider, Ekosme was selected for its strong expertise in web development, the quality of its previous projects, and its capacity to deliver a high-performance, user-oriented website. The choice of a regional provider also enhances responsiveness and supports local collaboration.

The development of the LipAgg website integrates the principles of the MSCA Green Charter, promoting environmentally sustainable digital practices:

- Implementation of **digital sobriety principles**, ensuring a lightweight and efficient website design
- Optimization of resource usage (e.g. Image compression, code minification and performance optimization ...)
- **Limitation of external server requests** to reduce environmental impact
- Use of **energy-efficient hosting infrastructure in France (O2Switch)**

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The website is compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring responsible and transparent data processing:

- Collection and processing of personal data **limited to specific purposes** (e.g. Newsletter)
- **Transparency towards users** regarding how and why their data is used
- Respect of user rights in accordance with EU regulations:
 - Right of access
 - Right to rectification
 - Right to object to data processing
- Implementation of measures to ensure **data confidentiality and integrity**
- Availability of a **clear privacy and cookie policy**, regularly updated and aligned with applicable regulations

LipAgg header:

The homepage banner illustrates amyloid fibers and was generated using artificial intelligence, providing a visually engaging representation aligned with the project's scientific focus and the visual identity.

LipAgg footer:

Program

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Quick Links

[Home](#)

[Projects Apply Now](#)

[Team](#)

[Partners](#)

[News & Events](#)

Subscribe to our Newsletter:

Your e-mail address is only used to send you our newsletter and information about the activities of LIPAGG. You can use the unsubscribe link.

Subscribe

LipAgg

Coordinated by
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) – France

MSCA Green Charter
The MSCA Green Charter sets out guiding principles promoting environmentally sustainable practices.

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LipAgg home page:

Welcome on LipAgg

LipAgg is a European Doctoral Network, aiming to unravel the structural complexities of amyloid protein-lipid aggregates and to investigate their role in pathological aggregation, cellular toxicity, and intercellular spread.

This ambitious project brings together a diverse team of **European experts** in biophysics, molecular biology, biochemistry, and computational biochemistry.

Our doctoral candidates will receive **interdisciplinary training**, gaining hands-on experience with state-of-the-art methodologies and working closely **with both academic institutions and industry partners**.

Through LipAgg, **we are funding 15 PhD projects** to tackle one of the key molecular questions behind major diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and type 2 diabetes.

Our doctoral candidates will combine cutting-edge approaches to understand **how harmful amyloid-lipid complexes form, how they damage cell membranes, and how they spread between cells**.

Hartmut Sebesse, MPINA (Germany)

Supported by **a consortium of 23 partners across 6 countries**, LipAgg doctoral researchers will collaborate within a vibrant international network—sharing expertise and technologies on science.

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Follow us on Social Media:

LipAgg consortium

An interactive map has been incorporated in the home page of LipAgg website, to showcase the geographic distribution of the consortium, including all partners and beneficiaries across Europe, **highlighting both the strong collaborative dimension** of the project and its pan-European reach.

Projects page:

The website **centralizes all Doctoral Network positions** and provides candidates with detailed information on the research topics, host institutions, and non-academic partners.

Links allow applicants to be redirected either to the application form or to the relevant contact email.

[HOME](#) [PROJECTS](#) [TEAM](#) [PARTNERS](#) [NEWS & EVENTS](#)

List of offered PhD projects for doctoral candidates (DC)

DC1 project: Characterisation of Aβ-lipid complexes.	DC2 project: Structural characterisation of α5-lipid complexes.	DC3 project: Biophysical characterisation of AβP-lipid Complexes in Type 2 Diabetes.
DC4 project: In Silico characterisation of AβP-lipid and α5-lipid complexes and design and synthesis of inhibitors.	DC5 project: Structural characterisation of lipid-associated AβP and Aβ Fibrils in Type 2 Diabetes and Alzheimer's Disease.	DC6 project: NMR structure of Aβ ₁₋₄₂ complex of AβP and its effect on fibrils and membranes.
DC7 project: Effect of Amyloid Protein-Lipid (Aβ-L) complexes on astrocyte-mediated synaptic and cell-to-cell propagation.	DC8 project: Design and synthesis of inhibitors of α-synuclein aggregation and α-synuclein-lipid interaction.	DC9 project: Investigating the cellular toxicity of α5, Aβ and AβP lipid complexes in pancreatic cells and EPSC derived neurons through multi-parametric metabolic and cell death assays.

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LipAgg team:

The “team” refers to the beneficiaries. Not all Principal Investigators are shown in this screenshot.

LipAgg team

The screenshot displays six team members in a 3x2 grid. Each member's profile includes a photo, name, title, affiliation logo, a list of roles and publications, and a 'View biography' button.

- Lucie Khemtemourian**: Coordinator & Principal Investigator, CNRS. Roles: Assistant Professor, Faculty Member of F-AMMIST Working, Faculty Head of Campus, Faculty Head of section 'Immunity' (Director: Michel Roméo), Faculty Head of group within F-AMMIST working committee, Faculty Artist: Health Activities.
- Emilie Fontaine**: European Project Manager, CNRS. Roles: Assistant Professor, Faculty Member of F-AMMIST Working, Faculty Head of group 'Immunity', Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Assistant: Health Activities, Faculty Assistant: Document.
- Carmelo La Rosa**: Principal Investigator, Universitè di Cagliari. Roles: Faculty Member: Health, Faculty Member of F-AMMIST Working, Faculty Head of group 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Immunity' (Director: Michel Roméo), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian).
- Birgit Strodel**: Principal Investigator, JELIICH. Roles: Faculty Assistant: Health, Faculty Member of F-AMMIST Working, Faculty Head of group 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Immunity' (Director: Michel Roméo), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian).
- Christian Griesinger**: Principal Investigator, HIRSHNER. Roles: Faculty Assistant: Health, Faculty Member of F-AMMIST Working, Faculty Head of group 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Immunity' (Director: Michel Roméo), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian).
- Anna Erländsson**: Principal Investigator, HIRSHNER. Roles: Faculty Assistant: Health, Faculty Member of F-AMMIST Working, Faculty Head of group 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Immunity' (Director: Michel Roméo), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian), Faculty Head of section 'Protein: Nucle' (Director: Lucie Khemtemourian).

LipAgg partners:

To enhance partners' visibility, the website includes a page featuring each partner along with direct links to their respective websites.

The screenshot shows the 'LipAgg partners' page. At the top is a navigation menu with links for HOME, PROJECTS, TEAM, PARTNERS, and NEWS & EVENTS. Below the menu is a text block describing the project's multidisciplinary and highly complementary consortium. At the bottom, there is a grid of logos for the following partners: UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN, BIOARCTIC, BiosolveIT, BRUKER, hhu, labobot, PARKINSON Research, AMNOVERSE, universitè BORDEAUX, PolyPeptide, Research, Schrödinger, and Plasseraud.

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Projects News & Events:

To meet communication and dissemination requirements, a dedicated section of the website is devoted to news, events, and publications.

News & Events

Kick-off meeting Online

Date : 26th - 27th March

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4. Social networks and open access science profiles

LipAgg has a LinkedIn page aimed **at promoting its activities, building a strong and active network**, and sharing doctoral positions and fellows' updates.

The overall goal is to create a **truly dynamic European research network** and to increase the impact and reach of the project.

This will serve as an additional communication channel to keep both project members (doctoral candidates and partners) and external audiences informed about ongoing activities and key updates.

LipAgg has a Zenodo repository. **Zenodo will be used as an open-access repository** to store, preserve, and share the project's research outputs. It will allow LipAgg to make publications, datasets, presentations, and other scientific materials freely accessible to the wider research community and the public. By ensuring long-term preservation and providing stable digital identifiers (DOIs), **Zenodo will also support transparency, reproducibility, and the dissemination of results beyond the consortium.**

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<https://LipAgg.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/LipAgg/>

zenodo

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